

Modelling Stock Market Volatility in India: A GARCH Analysis of the Nifty 50 Index

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The present study aims to examine the return and volatility patterns of the Indian stock market. The analysis is based on daily closing prices of the Nifty 50 index collected from the official website of Investing.com for the period from 1 April 2002 to 31 March 2024. The return and volatility behavior of the market was analyzed using the GARCH model. The results indicate that the Nifty 50 index generated positive and statistically significant returns over the study period. The findings further confirm that the conditional variance of returns is influenced by both lagged error terms and lagged conditional variance, validating the presence of volatility clustering in the Indian stock market. These findings provide important implications for investors and traders in formulating effective investment strategies to achieve abnormal returns.

Keywords: Return, volatility, GARCH, abnormal returns

The Indian stock market is a well-established stock market in the Asian region and is regulated by the SEBI, i.e., the Securities and Exchange Board of India. It serves as a platform for trading financial assets and functions as a vital link between investors, who act as savers, and entrepreneurs, who seek funds. It mobilises funds directly from investors to entrepreneurs while simultaneously providing liquidity to investors. In this way, the stock market plays a crucial role in the economic development of a country by ensuring appropriate allocation of its resources, thereby contributing to the long-term economic growth of the country. Essentially, the stock market facilitates the channelling of household savings into corporate and government sectors, contributing to overall economic expansion (Raut & Kumar, 2018).

Over time, the Indian stock market has experienced substantial changes due to regulatory reforms, technological progress, and increasing globalisation, making it attractive to both domestic and international investors. Despite this progress, the market continues to exhibit high volatility and complex return behaviour, which

necessitates careful analysis for informed investment decision-making. Volatility, commonly used as a measure of risk, is defined as the standard deviation of stock returns from their mean value and reflects the variability in market returns (Kaur, 2004). Simply put, higher volatility indicates greater fluctuations in returns and, consequently, higher risk (Khera et al., 2022). The returns and volatility of the Indian stock market depend on various factors like economic, social, and political factors such as inflation, interest rates, government tax policies, international trade, economic growth, business conditions, and GDP (Yadav, 2017). Numerous studies such as Dhankhar et al. (2025a), Dhankhar et al. (2025b), and Agarwal and Dhankhar (2024) have examined return and volatility patterns in the stock market and identified various stylised facts, including volatility clustering, persistence, and leverage effects, which assist investors in making well-informed decisions. Therefore, a thorough understanding of these patterns is essential for proper investment decisions and for identifying potential investment opportunities. Hence, the current study investigated the returns and volatility in the Indian stock market.

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Review of Literature

Goudarzi and Ramanarayanan (2011) examined the presence of asymmetric volatility in the Indian stock market by using the BSE 500 index as a representative measure. The study analyzed daily index data spanning the period from 2000 to 2009. To capture the differential influence of good and bad shocks on return volatility, asymmetric GARCH models, namely TGARCH (1,1) and EGARCH (1,1), were employed. The findings provided strong evidence of a leverage effect in the BSE 500 index, indicating that negative news exerted more influence on volatility as compared to that of positive shocks. This finding highlights the significant role of news asymmetry in shaping stock market volatility, with adverse information intensifying market fluctuations more than favorable news.

Mall et al. (2011) investigated the time-varying volatility behavior in the Indian futures market for the period June 2000 to May 2011. The study utilized daily closing prices of the index

obtained from the official website of the National Stock Exchange (NSE). Volatility dynamics were analyzed using GARCH models. The findings revealed a high degree of persistence in volatility. Moreover, results from the EGARCH and TGARCH models confirmed the presence of asymmetric volatility, with a pronounced leverage effect suggesting that negative market news led to a disproportionate increase in futures market volatility.

Tripathy and Garg (2013) analyzed the dynamic relationship of risk and return in six major emerging stock markets, namely India, Brazil, China, Mexico, Russia, and South Africa. The study employed daily closing price data of the respective stock indices, collected from the Money control database, covering the period from January 1999 to May 2010. Volatility was modeled using GARCH-M (1,1), EGARCH (1,1), and TGARCH (1,1) frameworks. The results indicated that both recent and past information significantly influenced volatility across all six markets, with persistent volatility shocks observed in each case. While a positive risk-return relationship was evident only in the Brazilian market, the Indian stock market exhibited a negative relation between returns and volatility, implying discounted risk in returns. Additionally, the presence of a leverage effect was confirmed across all emerging markets, indicating that negative information generated higher volatility than positive information.

Mathur et al. (2016) explored the effect of the global financial crisis on volatility in the Indian stock market by analyzing daily price data of the top 20 companies. The study covered the period from January 1, 2001, to October 15, 2012, and divided the data into four sub-periods: 2001-2003, 2004-2006, 2007-2009, and 2010-2012, to capture different market phases. Conditional heteroscedasticity was addressed using the GARCH model. The findings revealed a sharp increase in volatility during the 2007-2009 period, indicating that the Indian stock market was significantly and immediately affected by the global financial crisis.

Singh and Tripathi (2016) examined volatility patterns that existed in the stock market of India using daily closing prices of the Nifty 50 index. The analysis spanned fifteen years, from April 1, 2001, to March 31, 2016, and employed both symmetric and asymmetric GARCH models. Based on Akaike Information Criterion, Schwarz Information Criterion, and log-likelihood values, the GARCH-M (1,1) and EGARCH (1,1) models were the most appropriate models. The results revealed persistent volatility in the Indian stock market; however, volatility did not significantly influence expected returns, suggesting the absence of a conventional risk-return trade-off. Furthermore, the presence of a leverage effect was confirmed.

Endri et al. (2021) investigated the impact of COVID-19 on Indonesia's stock market using a combination of event study methodology and GARCH modelling. The study analyzed daily closing prices of 38 companies listed in the LQ-45 index. The event window included 40 days prior to the pandemic announcement, the event day, and 10 days following the event, with overall data spanning from January 6, 2020, to March 16, 2020. The results obtained from the GARCH (1,2) model indicated a significant rise in volatility during the pandemic period, which negatively affected abnormal returns. The study concluded that the COVID-19 outbreak had a substantial destabilizing effect on stock market volatility.

Trivedi et al. (2021) analyzed volatility behavior in the Indian stock market by examining the S&P BSE Large-Cap Index using

daily closing price data collected from the official website of the Bombay Stock Exchange for the period January 2005 to May 2020. The study employed GARCH models to capture volatility dynamics. The findings demonstrated the persistence of volatility shocks and confirmed the presence of a leverage effect.

Khera et al. (2022) examined volatility patterns across eleven sectoral indices in the Indian stock market using daily data from January 1, 2014, to December 31, 2019. The ARCH effect was detected in only five indices, namely Nifty Auto, Nifty IT, Nifty Metal, Nifty Media, and Nifty Realty. Volatility for these indices was modeled using symmetric GARCH (1,1) and GARCH-in-Mean (1,1) models. The results revealed persistent volatility across all selected indices, with the highest persistence observed in the Nifty Media index and the lowest in the Nifty Realty index. The study also found that long-term shocks were more persistent than short-term shocks. Additionally, a significant risk premium was observed only for the Nifty Metal index, indicating that higher volatility was compensated by higher returns in this sector.

Wang et al. (2022) analysed volatility behaviour in the Chinese stock market using daily closing price data of the Shanghai Composite Index and the Shenzhen Component Index obtained from the Guotai'an Financial Database for the period from January 4, 2000, to March 4, 2020. The study applied ARMA-GARCH models with different lag structures and error distributions. The ARMA (4,4)-GARCH (1,1) model under the student's t-distribution was found to be the best fit for the Shanghai Composite Index, while the ARMA (1,1)-TGARCH (1,1) model was most appropriate for the Shenzhen Component Index. The findings indicated persistent volatility that gradually declined over time. Furthermore, the presence of a leverage effect reflected information asymmetry, with market news exerting a stronger influence on the volatility of the Shenzhen Component Index compared to the Shanghai Composite Index.

Method

The present study adopted an analytical and descriptive technique. Secondary data were utilized to examine stock market returns and volatility behavior. To fulfill the objective, daily closing prices of the Nifty 50 index were used for the period spanning from April 1, 2002, to March 31, 2024. The index data were obtained from the official websites of Investing.com. The Nifty 50 was chosen due to its substantial representation of the Indian equity market, jointly accounting for nearly 69 percent of the free-float market capitalization of stocks listed on the NSE as of September 29, 2023.

Analytical Tools and Techniques Adopted for Secondary Data

The time series data was analyzed using the EViews 10 software. For analyzing the time series data, the data should be stationary. In case of non-stationarity of the data, log differencing return was calculated in order to make the data stationary, and thereafter, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was conducted to test the stationarity of the data.

Return of Data

Return of the series was computed by log differencing the given time series which is shown below:

$$R_t = \ln \left(\frac{p_t}{p_{t-1}} \right)$$

Where

R_t = return of the series at time t,

p_t = closing price of the indices at time t,

p_{t-1} = closing price of the indices at time t-1 and

ln = natural logarithm.

GARCH (1,1) Model for the Returns and Volatility of the Indian Stock Market

The GARCH model, proposed by Bollerslev (1986) posits that the conditional variance of a series depends on its own past values as well as on the lagged squared residuals. Among the various specifications of the GARCH family, the GARCH (1,1) model is the most commonly employed for modelling financial time series. The mean and variance equations of the GARCH (1,1) model are presented below.

Mean Equation

$$R_t = c + \alpha R_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where

R_t is return of the series at time t

R_{t-1} is return of series at time t-1

c is the average value of the return series over the time period and

α is the coefficient of lagged return.

ε_t is shock at time t

Variance Equation

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2$$

Where

σ_t^2 = conditional variance at time t,

ω, α, β = parameters to be estimated and

ω = constant conditional variance,

α & β = coefficients of ARCH and GARCH parameters respectively

ε_{t-1}^2 & σ_{t-1}^2 = the ARCH & GARCH parameters respectively

ε_t = shock in the return or white noise at time t

Results

Nature of the Daily Data of Selected Indices of NSE and BSE

The nature of the data has been analysed by plotting the price movement of Nifty 50 index, which is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Daily Price Movement of Nifty 50

Figure 1 depicts an overall upward trend in the index price series over the study period, indicating the presence of non-stationarity in the data. To address this issue and achieve stationarity, returns were computed by taking the natural logarithm of price relatives.

Nature of Daily Returns of Selected NSE and BSE Indices

The characteristics of the return series were examined by plotting the movements of daily returns over the study period. Figure 2 illustrates the daily returns of the Nifty 50 index.

Figure 2

Daily Returns of Nifty 50

The figure indicates that the return series display mean-reverting behavior, suggesting that returns fluctuate around a constant mean while exhibiting time-varying variance. Periods of high volatility are observed to be followed by further periods of high volatility, whereas periods of low volatility tend to be followed by similarly low volatility. This pattern confirms the presence of volatility clustering in the return series. Consequently, the series is found to be stationary.

Presence of Unit Root in the Daily Returns of Selected Stock Indices

Testing for the presence of a unit root is a fundamental step in assessing the stationarity of data, which is checked by ADF test as reported in Table 1.

Table 1

ADF Test

Index	t-statistics	Prob.
Nifty 50	-70.55743*	0.0001

Note. * significant at 5% level

The results revealed that the p-values were less than 0.05, indicating the absence of a unit root. Consequently, the null hypothesis of a unit root was rejected. These results confirm the stationary nature of the return series.

Analysis of Heteroscedasticity Using the ARCH-LM test

Table 2

ARCHEffect in Daily Returns of Indices

Index	t-statistics	Prob.
Nifty 50	279.2396*	0.0000

Note. * significant at 5% level

The F-statistic for the Nifty 50 was 279.2396. The corresponding probability values of the F-statistics were significant at the 1 percent level. Thus, results confirm the presence of ARCH effects in the residuals of the return series.

Analysis of the GARCH (1,1) Model for the Returns and Volatility of the Nifty 50

The GARCH (1,1) model with a Student's t-distribution was

employed. The results of the estimation are presented in Table 3. The analysis revealed that all estimated parameters were statistically significant at the 1 percent significance level.

The mean equation results show that the Nifty 50 index recorded a positive and statistically significant average return of 0.000892 at the 1 percent level. Lagged returns also significantly influenced current returns, indicating short-term predictability.

Table 3
GARCH (1,1) Model for Daily Returns of Nifty 50

Mean equation				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. error	Z-statistics	Prob.
C	0.000892	0.000124	7.183763	0.000
Return (-1)	0.069837	0.014161	4.931459	0.000
Variance equation				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. error	Z-statistics	Prob.
	2.02E-06	4.06E-07	4.97287	0.000
RESID (-1) ²	0.091054	0.008357	10.89529	0.000
GARCH (-1)	0.897597	0.008709	103.0614	0.000
T-DIST. DOF	7.455677	0.653873	11.40233	0.000
Model Fitness Statistics				
R-square	0.000746	S.D. dependent var	0.013575	
Adjusted R-square	0.000563	Akaike info criterion	-6.21817	
Log-likelihood	16984.72	Schwarz criterion	-6.21092	
Durbin-Watson	2.041803	Hannan-Quinn criteria	-6.21564	
Residual Diagnosis				
Heteroscedasticity Test: ARCH -LM Test				
F-statistics	0.686349	Prob. F (1,5458)	0.4074	
Obs*R-squared	0.686514	Prob. Chi-square (1)	0.4074	

Note. ω represents constant conditional variance, RESID (-1)² represents coefficient of ARCH term (α) and GARCH(-1) represents coefficient of GARCH term β

In the variance equation, all parameters were positive and significant at the 1 percent level. The ARCH and GARCH coefficients were 0.091054 and 0.897597, respectively, suggesting that volatility was driven more by past volatility than by new market shocks. The sum of these coefficients (0.988651) indicates strong volatility persistence, with shocks decaying slowly over time.

The ARCH-LM test on squared residuals showed no remaining ARCH effect, confirming the adequacy and good fit of the GARCH (1,1) model.

Discussion and Conclusion

The study examined the return and volatility behavior of the Indian stock market by analyzing the Nifty 50 index from April 1, 2002, to March 31, 2024, using the GARCH (1,1) framework. The resulting return series was found to be stationary and exhibited volatility clustering. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test further confirmed stationarity, as the p-value was less than 0.05. The returns and volatility of the selected indices were subsequently analyzed using GARCH models. A key prerequisite for applying GARCH models is the presence of ARCH effects, which was confirmed by the ARCH-LM test. The statistically significant p-values indicated the existence of ARCH effects in the residuals obtained from regressing returns on their lagged values. This heteroscedastic nature of the

return series was effectively captured through GARCH models. The results showed that the index generated positive and statistically significant returns throughout the study period, and these returns were significantly influenced by their past values. Such findings indicate an overall upward movement in the stock market and reflect favorable market conditions and investor confidence during the study period.

The results are consistent with the concept of persistence in financial time series, suggesting that past returns play an important role in predicting future returns. In the variance equations, both the ARCH and GARCH coefficients were statistically significant. A significant ARCH coefficient implies that new information related to past volatility affected current volatility, while a significant GARCH coefficient indicates that past volatility had a strong influence on present volatility. These findings confirm that the conditional variance of returns depends on both lagged error terms and lagged conditional variance.

The findings are in line with Adesina (2013) who reported that both news about previous volatility and past volatility itself influenced current volatility in the Nigerian stock market. The present study further indicates that the impact of past volatility on current volatility is stronger than the effect of new market information, implying that volatility is more sensitive to existing

volatility conditions. Consequently, volatility shocks in the Indian stock market exhibit a high degree of persistence. Similar evidence of volatility persistence has been reported for emerging markets such as Poland, Hungary, Turkey and the Czech Republic (Ugurlu et al., 2014).

Thus, it is concluded that stock market returns are significantly influenced by their lagged values, while volatility is more responsive to past volatility than to new market information, highlighting the persistent nature of volatility.

References

- Adesina, K. S. (2013). Modelling stock market return volatility: GARCH evidence from Nigerian stock exchange. *International Journal of Financial Management*, 3(3), 37-46.
- Agarwal, A., & Dhankhar, N. (2024). Analysing the impact of volatility decay on forecasted returns using ARMA, symmetric and asymmetric GARCH and TGARCH models. *European Economic Letters*, 14, 33-43.
- Bollerslev, T. (1986). Generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity. *Journal of Econometrics*, 31(3), 307-327.
- Dhankhar, N., Fakhra, S., Mehla, S., Tabash, M. I., & Asna Prestianawati, S. (2025b). Evidence of adaptive market hypothesis in the Indian stock market through analysing day of the week effect. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 13(1), 2571402.
- Dhankhar, N., Sharma, A., & Mehla, S. (2025a). Exploring the day of the week effect in the Indian stock market: Insights from symmetric and asymmetric GARCH models. *Al-Barkaat Journal of Finance and Management*, 13(2), 68-83.
- Endri, E., Aipama, W., Razak, A., Sari, L., and Septiano, R. (2021). Stock price volatility during the COVID-19 pandemic: The GARCH model. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 18(4), 12-20.
- Goudarzi, H., & Ramanarayanan, C. S. (2011). Modeling asymmetric volatility in the Indian stock market. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(3), 221-231.
- Kaur, H. (2004). Time varying volatility in the Indian stock market. *Vikalpa*, 29(4), 25-42.
- Khera, A., Goyal, A., and Yadav, M. P. (2022). Capturing the stock market volatility: A study of sectoral indices in India using symmetric GARCH models. *International Journal of Management Practice*, 15(6), 820-833.
- Mall, M., Pradhan, B., and Mishra, P. (2011). The efficiency of India's stock index futures market: An empirical analysis. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 69, 178-184.
- Mathur, S., Chotia, V., and Rao, N. V. M. (2016). Modelling the impact of global financial crisis on the Indian stock market through GARCH models. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 12(1), 11-22.
- Raut, R. K., & Kumar, R. (2018). Investment decision-making process between different groups of investors: A study of Indian stock market. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 14(1-2), 39-49.
- Singh, S., & Tripathi, L. K. (2016). Modelling stock market return volatility: Evidence from India. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(13), 93-101.
- Tripathy, N., & Garg, A. (2013). Forecasting stock market volatility: Evidence from six emerging markets. *Journal of International Business and Economy*, 14(2), 69-93.
- Trivedi, J., Afjal, M., pulbar, C., Birau, R., Inumula, K.M., & Pradhan (2021). Modeling emerging stock market volatility using asymmetric GARCH family models: AN empirical case study for BE Ltd. (formerly known as Bombay stock exchange) of India. *Revista de Stiinte Politice*, 70, 167-176.
- Ugurlu, E., Thalassinou, E., & Muratoglu, Y. (2014). Modeling volatility in the stock markets using GARCH models: European emerging economies and Turkey. *International Journal in Economics and Business Administration*, 2(3), 72-87.
- Wang, Y., Xiang, Y., Lei, X., & Zhou, Y. (2022). Volatility analysis based on GARCH-type models: Evidence from the Chinese stock market. *Economic Research-Ekonomika Istraživanja*, 35(1), 2530-2554.
- Yadav, S. (2017). Stock Market Volatility: A study of Indian stock market. *Global Journal for Research Analysis*, 6(4), 629-632.

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